

Review of Heat Generation and Liquid Based Cooling Techniques in GPUs

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Keywords : Immersion Cooling , GPU , Liquid Cooling , Thermal Waste , Heat Sink, throttling

Abstract : Heat generation in GPUs today has become a serious threat to its efficient working. Many cooling methods have been designed today to tackle this problem of thermal waste generation but none has been more successful and widely accepted than the Liquid Cooling techniques. Three major Liquid cooling methods include : Immersion , close loop and custom built liquid cooling . These methods have been discussed in detail in this paper and light has been thrown on the causes , effects and methods of cooling techniques in this paper. The paper gives information about the background and history of GPU components and also discusses the superiority of liquid cooling over air cooling with proven data and statistics. Moreover , this paper discusses the future of liquid cooling in the GPU world including reducing costs, system optimisation and method practicality.

INTRODUCTION

Graphics Processing Units(GPUs) have been around for a long time now. From the earliest GPU(Nvidia's GeForce 256) [1] in 1999 to the latest RTX 50 Series in 2025 , GPUs have seen astronomical growth in their processing power.

To tackle the problem of heat generation in GPUs , several cooling techniques have been adapted. The simplest method being the heatsink and fan combination which has been used in all of the consumer level GPUs since they are cost effective and require low maintenance. On the industrial scale, since the spike in GPU demand following the AI revolution in the past few years, an effective cooling technique has become a necessity.

Open AI's GPT-3 model evaporated around 700,000 litres of freshwater for its training[2].

But alongside the primitive method of using a fan, various other methods have been devised to appreciably cool down our system much more effectively. As noted in [3], with reference to water cooling , "There are three major classifications of cooling system and they are: water cooling, close loop liquid cooling, and immersion cooling systems ."

These latest new generation cooling methods are now being adapted for better cooling and in turn a better GPU performance.

Immersion cooling has become the new trend in today's world[8]. Along with its moderate maintenance cost, it has proven to be the most effective method of cooling to address the issue of thermal buildup. China, taking the lead in immersion cooling, has become the world's first nation to set up its data centre in the ocean[4]. With nature acting as a catalyst, China's endeavours in minimising thermal waste seems like a promising possibility.

This paper reviews the causes and effects of heat generation in GPUs and explores three major liquid cooling techniques—immersion, closed-loop, and custom liquid loops—highlighting their efficiency and practical adoption. The paper also sheds some light on various components of a GPU. The paper's aim is to provide a basic understanding of the above stated problem and its solutions by referring to various research papers. The data and information used has been verified and appropriate references have been given wherever required.

METHODOLOGY

Sources of Information

This review on "Heat generation and cooling techniques in graphics processing units" has been made by referencing credible sources of information. All the images used have been downloaded from public domains on Wikipedia.

The various sources of information on the topic have been mentioned below:

- Websites such as Google scholar, arXiv.org
- Youtube Channels: Branch Education, ElectroBOOM,

BACKGROUND

GPU Components and an inside view of the Heat Generation

A typical NVIDIA 3090 graphics card used the GA102 chip design. The GA102 GPU includes 28.3 billion transistors with a die size of 628.4 mm²[5]. The incoming 12V power connector is connected to the Voltage Regulator Module which converts the incoming 12Volts into 1.1Volts and supplies it to the GPU. The RTX 3090 consumes 350 watts of power, majority of which is converted into heat[6]. Alongside the high power consumption, the GPU is fitted with billions of transistors which are switched on and off continuously resulting in thermal waste development. According to NVIDIA Architecture, the majority area of the GA102 chip is occupied by the processing cores, specifically, the chip is divided into 7 Graphics Processing Clusters(GPCs) and each cluster has 12 Streaming Multiprocessors(SMs). Inside each Streaming Multiprocessor are 4 Warps and 1 Ray Tracing Core. Inside each Warp are 32 CUDA cores and 1 Tensor core. These cores perform trillions of calculations per second which causes significant heat generation.

The need for Cooling

The modern day consumer grade GPUs are being cooled by a simple fan and heat sink system. The 350 watt [5] power consumption of the RTX 3090 calls for a better cooling system than the native fan. Modern day tasks like- Running games with realistic graphics, real life ray tracing, rendering 4K images and videos, consume a large amount of power which increases the risk of over heating[7]. This has created a need for new means of cooling GPU systems[8].

Different Cooling Methods

Due to recent technological advancements, air cooling is now not the sole method of maintaining your GPU temperature under control.

Immersion Cooling - A more efficient and advanced cooling method being used today is the immersion cooling method[8].

Fig. 1. The temperature difference between fan and immersion cooling experiment[9]

In Fig.1. we can see that after three minutes, the GPU reached a stable working temperature and this calls for the comparison of the temperature measurements. Using a cooling fan, GPU reached a temperature of 80°C while the use of immersion cooling shows that the temperature measurement of the GPU was 60°C with the same benchmark. From the graph, it can be deduced that there is a difference of up to 20°C when immersion cooling method is used compared to the conventional cooling method[9].

Close Loop Liquid Cooling (AIO)

It involves a coolant which is made to flow through a flexible tubing which in turn cool's down the system components with the help of a cold plate which connects the electronic module and allows for the transfer of heat into the coolant[9,10].

The overall liquid cooling system consists of the following key components:

- Pump
- Cold plates
- Heat Exchanger
- Flexible Tubing
- Coolant

Fig.2. Working of Close Loop Liquid Cooling

Custom Liquid Cooling Loops

These are fully custom made liquid cooling loops tailored for an individual's GPU. The coolant is often user filled and requires regular maintenance[10]. Unlike regular AIO coolers, these are fully customizable as per a user's requirement.

Comparative Analysis

Table 1.

<u>Feature</u>	<u>Close Loop Liquid Cooling</u>	<u>Custom Liquid Cooling Loops</u>	<u>Immersion Cooling</u>
Cooling Capacity	The Closed Loop offers a moderate to high Cooling performance of around 300 watts.	They can handle very high cooling wattage(>500watts).	They can handle extremely high cooling (used for data centres)
Installation Complexity	Easy	Moderate	High
Maintenance	Very Low	High	Moderate
Customizability	None	High	Low
Noise	Low to Moderate	Very Low	Negligible

Cost	Low	Moderate	High
Risk of leak	Low	Moderate	None
Use Case	4k Gaming, Graphics rendering	PC enthusiast , overclockers , custom PC builder	Crypto mining farm, data centres

Discussions

1. Heat Generation (Impacts) :

Clock speed of a GPU refers to the frequency at which its processor operates , it is usually measured in MHz or GHz. Faster clock speed is required in GPUs to quickly process real time rendering , AI driven tasks , or proceed with real time simulations. When a GPU runs , heat is conceived as an unwanted byproduct which must be removed to avoid thermal damage and throttling. When a GPU's temperature exceeds a certain threshold , its clock speed will automatically get reduced to prevent thermal damage.

It is important to maintain temperature of GPU in order to :

- Provide a consistent performance
- Increase the lifespan of GPUs
- Increase efficient energy consumption

All these reasons account for better cooling measures on top of sufficient cooling and airflow , automated monitoring and AI driven solutions and using efficient data centre design.

2. Cooling Methods :

The above provided information shows how modern liquid cooling methods are proving to be more efficient and better than the traditional air cooling. Liquid having high specific heat capacity in turn absorb more heat from the system components than air[8]. It is also to be noted that medium coolants should have special properties which include : they must be non-inflammable , non-toxic and cheap[8]. On top of having appropriate physical and thermal properties, the material of the medium should be able to run well with the components of the GPU system.

Table 2. Heat transfer coefficient on gas and liquid objects[11]

Cooling Method	Heat transfer Coefficient from air(W / m ² K)	Heat transfer Coefficient From water (liquid)(W / m ² k)
Free Convection	5-100	100-1200
Forced Convection	10-350	500-3000
With Steam	-	3000-100000

The above table which has been adapted from [8] , clearly shows that immersion cooling is superior as the heat transfer coefficient of liquid is very high as compared to air.

Future Scope:

While liquid cooling has come out as a better alternative to air cooling, the future of GPU cooling techniques is evolving. Many new different forms of cooling techniques are being developed today.

To describe a few :

1. ***Dynamic Clock adjustment technology*** : NVIDIA's GPU now are releasing with an inbuilt thermal throttling mechanism which automatically detects and changes the GPU clock speed to maintain optimum temperature thus delivering maximum power output. This feature holds importance in fields such as AI training and data centres.
2. ***NVIDIA's NVLink for Temperature Balancing in Multi-GPU Systems*** : NVIDIA's NV Link facilitates faster communication between the GPU's making them work together in a more efficient manner , making it very crucial for multi GPU tasks like bitcoin mining or Data centres.

Conclusion

There has been tremendous improvement in the GPU sector in the past two decades. These improvements call for increased Thermal waste production and therefore an efficient cooling system was required to maintain the components temperature. This review paper has compiled information from different research papers , news articles and used imagery to depict and show the causes of heat generation in modern day GPU and also some measures to cool down systems efficiently. Liquid based cooling coming out as a clear victor over air cooling.

References

- [1] "GeForce 256," *Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia*. [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/GeForce_256
- [2] M. Anderson, "The Often Overlooked Water Footprint of AI Models," *Medium*, Feb. 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://generative-ai-newsroom.com/the-often-overlooked-water-footprint-of-ai-models-46991e3094b6>
- [3] H. Rafsanjani, A. Marwazi, Z. O. W. T. Gari, J. T. Sinaga, and D. Sitompul, "Thermal Management and Power Optimization in Modern CPU and GPU Architectures," Dec. 2024. [Online]. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/386476458_Thermal_Management_and_Power_Optimization_in_Modern_CPU_and_GPU_Architectures
- [4] Y. Xiaoying, "China Is Putting Data Centers in the Ocean to Keep Them Cool," *Scientific American*, Jul. 16, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/china-powers-ai-boom-with-undersea-data-centers/>
- [5] nvidia-ampere-ga-102-gpu-architecture-whitepaper-v2 , [Online]. Available : <https://www.nvidia.com/content/PDF/nvidia-ampere-ga-102-gpu-architecture-whitepaper-v2.pdf>
- [6] NVIDIA Ampere GA102 GPU Architecture , page 7 , [Online] . Available : <https://www.nvidia.com/content/PDF/nvidia-ampere-ga-102-gpu-architecture-whitepaper-v2.pdf>
- [7] "Nvidia's new Blackwell AI chips face issue with overheating servers" , business-standard.com , [Online] Available : https://www.business-standard.com/technology/tech-news/nvidia-s-new-blackwell-ai-chips-face-issue-with-overheating-servers-124111700587_1.html

[8] N. A. Pambudi, H. Bugis, I. W. Kuncoro, N. D. Setiawan, M. Hijriawan, B. Rudiyanto, and B. Basori, "Preliminary experimental of GPU immersion-cooling," *E3S Web of Conferences*, vol. 93, Art. no. 03003, 2019. doi: [10.1051/e3sconf/20199303003](https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/20199303003).

[9] Reprinted from N. A. Pambudi, H. Bugis, I. W. Kuncoro, N. D. Setiawan, M. Hijriawan, B. Rudiyanto, and B. Basori, "Preliminary experimental of GPU immersion-cooling," *E3S Web of Conferences*, vol. 93, Art. no. 03003, page 3 , figure 2,2019. doi: [10.1051/e3sconf/20199303003](https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/20199303003).

[10] S. Kang, D. Miller, and J. Cennamo, "Closed loop liquid cooling for high performance computer systems," in *Proc. ASME InterPACK '07*, Vancouver, BC, Canada, Jul. 2007. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1115/IPACK2007-33870>

[11] Adapted from N. A. Pambudi, H. Bugis, I. W. Kuncoro, N. D. Setiawan, M. Hijriawan, B. Rudiyanto, and B. Basori, "Preliminary experimental of GPU immersion-cooling," *E3S Web of Conferences*, vol. 93, Art. no. 03003, page 2 , table 1,2019. doi: [10.1051/e3sconf/20199303003](https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/20199303003).